

Olinto de Pretto a Citizen Scientist a Century Ago

Carlo Artemi ✉

Ministero Pubblica Istruzione, Italy

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Abstract

The paper is an examination by the author of the contents of a publication written by the Italian scholar Olinto De Pretto in 1904. This work was virtually unknown until it was cited a few years ago by the Italian professor Umberto Bartocci. Bartocci, who teaches the history of mathematics at the University of Peru, confirmed that De Pretto had written the mass-energy equivalence formula of special relativity in his paper a year before Einstein's famous article. Bartocci affirmed that Einstein could have understood formula by a friend of his who was a friend of De Pretto too Bartocci idea was not taken seriously. The author has now examined De Pretto's paper. In this paper De Pretto presented his vision of the universe as composed of matter and luminiferous ether in interaction with each other and both having an atomic structure. In this paper there are similarities with aspects of contemporary physics, including a formula formally equivalent to the most famous formula of Einstein's theory of relativity. However, De Pretto's vision is entirely internal to classical physics and is therefore surpassed by the facts. The figure of De Pretto, on the other hand, is very interesting and has strong similarities with the current phenomenon of citizen science.

Keywords: *Relativity, Einstein, De Pretto, contemporary physics, luminiferous ether, theories of gravity.*

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Introduction

It can happen that in historical studies unknown or little known aspects of important figures are discovered. This was the case with Newton's alchemical manuscripts (Newman, 2018). Or it can happen that unknown figures are discovered who instead made important contributions to scientific progress and beyond.

A few years ago, Prof. Umberto Bartocci, Professor of the History of Mathematics at the University of Perugia (Italy), stated (Bartocci, 2014) that an unknown Italian scholar, Olinto de Pretto, had written the relativistic formula $E=mc^2$ in a paper of his (De Pretto, 1904) one year before Einstein. Bartocci suggested that Einstein might also have learned

of De Pretto's formula from a mutual friend. Studies immediately carried out on De Pretto's paper quickly showed that there was only a formal similarity between the two formulas and that they had a completely different meaning. The author recently had the opportunity to read De Pretto's complete original paper and to learn more about him. Very interesting things emerged which do not confirm the Bartocci hypothesis, but are worthy of publication.

The De Pretto Paper

Olinto de Pretto was born in Schio (a small Italian town in the Veneto region) on 26-4-1857. Together with his brother Silvio, he founded a mechanical company that still exists today under a different name (Ivaldi, & Meijer, 2022). He was

a successful entrepreneur. Although he had a degree in agriculture, he always showed great interest in research in the field of physics and astronomy. He was in contact with the astronomer Schiapparelli. He had an excellent knowledge of classical physics and in particular of the luminiferous ether theory, which explained electromagnetic phenomena as mechanical phenomena of this imaginary medium. He was very well informed about the developments of scientific research. He knew a lot of astronomical data, he knew the existence of radioactive phenomena and the theory of the continuous contraction of the Sun. In his article he even quotes an almost forgotten experiment by Wheatstone, who had tried to measure the speed of electricity. Wheatstone had obtained a value of 465,000 kilometres per second, greater than the speed of light.

We now know (Lammertink 2020) that Wheatstone had measured an apparent speed, but at the time the result was taken seriously.

De Pretto died in 1921, the same year that Einstein won the Nobel Prize for Physics. Einstein won the prize for the photoelectric effect, not for relativity. This murder was for private reasons and has nothing mysterious about it.

He was killed by a woman, apparently for financial reasons. It must be remembered that this was a time of great social and political turmoil for Italy (Benito Mussolini would have marched on Rome in 1922) and there were frequent episodes of crime. Another famous industrialist, Marzotto (wikipedia.it), also born and living in Veneto, was killed that year.

The importance and topicality of De Pretto's figure will be discussed later.

For now, let's look at his paper.

It is a long paper in which he explains his vision of the universe, a universe in which the luminiferous ether plays a fundamental role. As we will see, it is a vision completely internal to classical physics, but with features of originality that seem to anticipate some elements of contemporary physics.

De Pretto thought that the universe was made up of matter and ether, and that both had a corpuscular nature. Matter was made up of macroscopic objects made up of molecules made up of atoms made up of subatomic particles. This vision may seem banal today, but at the time it was not. De Pretto does not explicitly speak of the electron, but it is very likely that he is referring to it. De Pretto thought that subatomic particles were much smaller than atoms, anticipating the discovery of the atomic nucleus that would be made ten years later in the Rutherford experiment.

According to De Pretto, even the ether was made up of atoms (obviously different from those of matter), and here De Pretto was not very original, this hypothesis had already been advanced years before, as can be understood from a speech by Maxwell quoted in an edition of a book by Einstein. However, De Pretto thought that both ether atoms and material atoms were in perpetual motion (thermal motion) and here he wrote the above formula, but he made a big mistake.

De Pretto thought that each ether atom had the same mass m and that, moving at a speed v , it had a kinetic energy trivially equal to mv^2 . Apart from the absence of the term $1/2$, De Pretto identified the speed of ether atoms with the speed of light. Obviously this is wrong, it is as if I identified the speed of the wind with the speed of sound. But if I identify v with the speed of light, I have a formula that is formally the same as Einstein's, but with a completely different meaning. In Einstein's theory of relativity, m is the rest mass of an object, which is equivalent to energy, and the formula quoted above expresses precisely this equivalence. Einstein wrote the formula, albeit implicitly, from a series of considerations about space-time and the invariance of physical laws for different observers. De Pretto fully accepted the Newtonian idea of an absolute Euclidean space-time and didn't have the problem of the invariance of physical laws for different observers. Einstein arrives at his formula through the Lorentz transformations, which De Pretto never mentions and probably didn't even know about.

Furthermore, it must be emphasised that De Pretto hypothesised a corpuscular nature of the ether, but not of light. In De Pretto's vision, light was a normal mechanical wave of a very specific medium. It is therefore not correct to say that De Pretto anticipated wave-particle dualism. His idea of light is consistent with classical physics.

The most interesting part of the article is De Pretto's attempt to explain the gravitational force as an effect of the interactions between matter and ether, partly because there is an attempt to reduce both the gravitational force and the force holding atoms and molecules together to a single force.

The reasoning is as follows. It is assumed that atoms, molecules and macroscopic objects are transparent to ether particles, but subatomic particles of matter aren't. An ether particle will therefore collide with a subatomic particle in an elastic collision.

It is easy to see that in this case, as can be seen in Figure 1 from the De Pretto paper (the arrows indicate the pressure of the ether and their length indicates the intensity of the pressure), there is an attractive force between the two particles that is proportional to the inverse of the square of their distance. There is a difference between the pressures exerted by the ether particles on the two opposite sides of the matter particles and this causes the force.

Figure 1. Example Referring to Gravitational Force
Source: De pretto paper

The intermolecular and interatomic forces are much stronger than the gravitational force simply because the distances involved are smaller. It is obvious that in order to reach this conclusion, De Pretto had to interpret the well-known gravitational formula in an unusual way.

The formula is as follows:

$$F = Gm_1m_2/r^2 \quad (1)$$

and, he had to interpret the gravitational masses m_1 and m_2 not so much as inertia, but as the number of subatomic particles present in the two objects that attract each other. Moreover, De Pretto's vision of gravity is more akin to the theory of Cartesian fluids in a universe full of matter than to the Newtonian vision of two objects in empty space. It is also evident that De Pretto does not consider electromagnetic forces as the cause of attraction between atoms and molecules. This fact is in the classical vision of electromagnetic phenomena caused by macroscopic movements of ether.

However, it must be recognised that the attempt to unify the forces, characteristic of the most recent physical theories, is already present in De Pretto. The distinction between material particles, which make up bodies, and ether particles, which create the forces between them, is reminiscent of the distinction between fermions and bosons, but it is obvious that this is only a similarity.

But De Pretto thought that the matter-ether interaction could also explain the heat of the sun and the stars.

It had long been known that the Sun's heat could not be produced by chemical combustion. The only theory that could explain the source of the Sun's energy before the discovery of nuclear reactions was the theory of continuous solar contraction, according to which the decrease in the Sun's gravitational potential energy produced heat. De Pretto was familiar with this theory and made some critical observations about it that did not seem original. He hypothesised, in partial contradiction to himself, that the continuous motion of the ether and material particles

created a form of friction and then heat. The problem was that this form of heat should be present in any object as long as it had a high mass. Therefore, one was forced to hypothesise that outer planets larger than the Earth should be hotter than the Earth, even if they were colder than the Sun. The astronomical observations available at the time were already sufficient to disprove this hypothesis.

De Pretto thought that even radioactive phenomena could be explained as a consequence of ether-matter interaction, but he left this as a hypothesis and did not go into it.

Conclusion

As you can see, De Pretto's vision of the universe, although original and with some similarities to contemporary physics, was entirely within classical physics and was contradicted by the facts.

However, if De Pretto's theory is not current, his figure is very interesting because he can be seen as a transitional figure between the "amateur" scientists of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries and the current phenomenon of citizen science.

In the centuries before the twentieth century, important scientific discoveries were made by people who were neither university professors nor researchers. Cavendish, the discoverer of hydrogen, had no connection with the university, Lavoisier was a financial official, and Einstein himself was an ordinary employee at the Patent Office when he wrote his famous articles.

Today, even complex research is carried out with an important contribution from "citizen scientists" (for more information, see <https://participatorysciences.org>), i.e. people who also have a scientific culture but do not work for universities or research institutions. It is important to stress that they are neither teachers nor popularisers, but active participants in research. They can do simple analyses of a lot of data (for example, photographs of galaxies), or they can run simulation programs on their PCs with data taken from websites, or they can collect material (for example, air samples in certain places and at certain times); material that is then analysed.

The combination of these activities is citizen science

De Pretto is clearly comparable to both the amateur scientists of earlier eras and the citizen scientists of today, and can therefore be seen as a transitional figure between the two eras.

He was an entrepreneur but with a considerable scientific culture, he was not a university professor but had contacts with professional researchers and was able to develop original theories and write articles that were considered worthy of publication.

It would be very important to know whether De Pretto was an isolated figure in those years or whether there were other "citizen scientists" like him. It would be interesting to check, perhaps by searching the historical archives of his company if they exist, whether as an entrepreneur he had contacts with the scientific world, for example by selling equipment for carrying out experiments to Italian or foreign universities.

In short, De Pretto is an interesting figure of the scientific world who deserves to be rediscovered, even if his vision of the universe has proved to be wrong and is now of historical interest only.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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